

Bot Detection via Drag-and-Drop Letter Rearrangement and Behavioral Analysis.

Author: Raul Popa

Affiliation: TypingDNA Inc.

Abstract

This work discloses a human verification and behavioral biometric method based on randomized sequence rearrangement. A word, alphanumeric, character, emoji, or unicode char sequence is selected and displayed in two forms: (1) its characters are shuffled and shown as draggable items on the screen, and (2) the correct sequence is faintly displayed in a placeholder row of slots (for example, in light grey) to guide the user. The user must reconstruct the sequence by dragging the shuffled characters into the placeholder.

During drag-and-drop, the system records behavioral signals. On desktop, this includes mouse movement, trajectory, path curvature, speed, hesitation, and timing between pickup and drop. On mobile devices, touch path features as well as motion sensor data (accelerometer and gyroscope), including motion sensor data related to pick and drop events, are captured during the drag interaction.

The solution functions in two modes: (a) as a standalone human challenge, which is inherently resistant to automation, and (b) as an enhanced biometric layer, distinguishing humans from bots through movement dynamics. This approach differs from known mouse dynamics biometrics and randomized virtual keyboards by uniquely combining drag-based sequence reconstruction with behavioral and motion data capture, providing a simple but robust defense against automated attacks.

Background

Automated bots and scripts increasingly bypass traditional CAPTCHAs and login defenses by using computer vision, pre-rendered solutions, or scripted API calls. Existing behavioral biometrics often focus on keystroke dynamics or mouse movement during free interaction. Randomized virtual keyboards are used against keyloggers, but they do not leverage behavioral data for verification. There is therefore a need for a lightweight method that is difficult to automate, easy for humans, and capable of generating rich behavioral signals for bot detection and authentication.

System Description

The invention introduces a method where a word or alphanumeric sequence is chosen and displayed to the user in two forms. First, the characters are shuffled and displayed in randomized positions as draggable items. Second, a placeholder row of slots is shown, with the correct sequence optionally rendered faintly in light grey to guide reconstruction. The user completes the challenge by dragging the shuffled characters into the slots in the correct order.

During drag-and-drop, the system records detailed behavioral data. On desktop systems, this includes mouse trajectories, path curvature, speed, acceleration, hesitation before release, and accuracy of placement. On mobile devices, touch paths and additional motion sensor signals from accelerometers and gyroscopes are recorded, especially at pickup and drop events. The combined dataset provides unique behavioral patterns for each user interaction.

Example Embodiments

1. **Desktop implementation:** The user sees shuffled characters on a web page and drags them using a mouse into the placeholder slots. Mouse trajectories and timing are recorded.
 2. **Mobile implementation:** The user drags letters with a finger, while the system records touch coordinates as well as motion sensor data (accelerometer and gyroscope data) throughout the drag.
 3. **Hybrid puzzles:** Instead of only letters, the shuffled set may contain numbers, unicode chars, emojis, or shapes, requiring arrangement into a target code or pattern.
 4. **Simplified version:** The behavioral analysis may be omitted, and the rearrangement itself serves as a challenge that is inherently hard to automate for bots.
-

Analysis Modes

The system can operate in two distinct modes:

- **Challenge Mode:** Completion of the rearrangement puzzle alone is sufficient to verify human presence.
 - **Biometric Mode:** In addition to correctness, the captured behavioral data is analyzed using statistical thresholds or machine learning models to further distinguish humans from bots or automated systems.
-

Applications

This method can be applied in multiple domains:

- Primarily
 - Bot detection / CAPTCHA replacement: A more user-friendly alternative to distorted text or image recognition challenges.
 - Fraud prevention: Detection of automated / scripted activity in online banking, e-commerce, and account creation systems.
- Secondary
 - Authentication: An additional factor in login flows, adding behavioral verification without requiring extra hardware.
 - Education and testing: Ensuring human participation in online exams or courses by requiring sequence rearrangements.

The system therefore provides both usability and security benefits, combining puzzle-solving with behavioral biometrics.

Novelty

This approach differs from prior art in several ways. Unlike standard mouse dynamics biometrics, the invention imposes a structured drag-and-drop task that generates consistent, comparable behavioral signals. Unlike randomized virtual keyboards, the system is designed not to primarily protect against keylogging, but to actively verify human presence. By combining sequence reconstruction with behavioral data capture, it creates a lightweight but robust anti-automation solution. The addition of motion sensor data on mobile platforms further strengthens the uniqueness of this method.